

The Representation of Gender Roles in Indonesian National English Textbooks for Senior High Schools

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Abstract

Learners internalize some values behind the materials and instruction provided in their textbooks. The values have a pivotal role in changing learners' beliefs, behaviors, and attitudes, however; numerous textbooks investigated embedded gender inequality values. This study explores gender representation in Senior High Schools textbooks published by the government of Indonesia. Three different textbooks for grades X, XI, and XII were used as a corpus in this study. A mixed content analysis was applied to analyze the data. Five categories namely visibility, firstness, social role, domestic roles, and masculine generic forms were counted, tabulated, and analyzed. The research results show that gender imbalance representation exists in the textbooks which showed by the males' illustrations, names, and pronouns men's representations have much more than women's representations. Plenty of images, symbols, and signs were illustrated by males' domination. Almost all pictures selected at the beginning of the chapter are men revealing men's power and domination in everyday life. While, women were described in domestic roles to be child caring, house cleaning, and sexual service, men are portrayed as soldiers, hunters, and breadwinners leading to power. Thus, it is concluded that gender inequality still exists in the textbooks although written by women, and the senior high school English textbooks still perpetuate of the gender inequality values in Indonesia.

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Keywords

Gender values, English textbooks, Senior High Schools, gender representations, gender inequality

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Introduction

Textbooks, modules, or other learning materials have a pivotal role in the teaching and learning process including learning English. The English language as an international language and global lingua franca is used widely in various cultural contexts, thus it is used to facilitate the teaching and learning process in classrooms (Liu et al., 2022) and textbooks developed to refer to world Englishes that have varieties of English spoken throughout the world (Mostafaei Alaei & Parsazadeh, 2021). Over the years, the textbooks and values embedded in the materials have undergone various transformations in response to the government and educational policy (Rahim & Daghigh, 2020). This situation has impacted the materials used in English Language Teaching (ELT) (Nguyen et al., 2021).

English has been dominant throughout the world in learning a foreign language in the education system for many years (Joo et al., 2020) because “it is advocated as a language of social prestige and economic value” (Nguyen et al., 2021, p.11). As a result, plenty of people learned it for many purposes, such as trade, politics, health, economics, and educational sectors. In response to the educational environment, materials and textbooks have critical elements in English Language Teaching. It is because the materials play crucial factors in shaping ideologies, perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes of the learners, in the other words “Language and ideology are inseparable from discourse” (Botelho & Marion, p.3, 2020). According to Orfan (2021) foreign language textbooks, e.g. English, has an essential role in teaching and learning the language that is not only to convey the language contents but also to transfer values, ideologies, and norms. Moreover, as an illustration, in Afghanistan, textbooks have a critical role in educational sectors to influence the learners’ perspectives so that the textbook developers use common language and use certain pictures in the texts to communicate (Sarvarzade & Wotipka, 2017). Textbooks are one of the cores of the teaching and learning process because they consist of materials, activities, and instructions for learning. However, numerous gender inequality frequently were identified in the textbooks (Barton & Sakwa, 2012; Lee, 2018; Lee & Collins, 2010; Orfan, 2021, Vu & Pham, 2021).

Gender stereotypes and patriarchy have an essential role in incorporating the values in the materials. Mai & Brundrett (2020) reveal that gender stereotypes and patriarchal attitudes have a big influence on the way people act and perceive society. It also includes influencing the learners’ how they treat people in their workplaces, Verge (2021, p.1) believes that “unawareness about how gender inequalities are (re)produced will inevitably lead the learners to become gender-blind doctors, teachers, engineers, policymakers, and other jobs”. Then this condition limit understanding of gender equality and the ways of the social construction of gender identities and has a close correlation to conflict (Durrani & Halai, 2018).

Textbooks have a significant element in changing pupils’ perspectives and attitudes in which one of the main goals in education is to pursue the learners to be better persons, to have open-minded perspectives, to have equal treatment (gender equality), and lead both females and males have the same opportunity to gain the brighter future. Consequently, it is important to analyse and scrutinize the materials related to the appropriateness of the contents and the pictures to the intended users (Bansiong, 2019). This research topic in Indonesia is scarce; therefore, this study aims to fill the gap by concerning textbooks of senior high schools for grades X, XI, and XII.

1. Literature Review

Textbooks are materials authority in which the ideas, values, and perspectives incorporated in the materials are influential to the readers or learners (Vu & Pham, 2021). Almost all written texts such

as textbooks or other materials have different purposes which are depended on the developers or writers' interests or goals. For instance, the English language used in the textbooks is consumerism, one of neoliberalism's main manifestation, so the ideology embedded in the textbooks is the neoliberalism values through the sentences (word choices) written (Daghigh & Rahim, 2021). As an example, they wrote (p.6) "It's very easy to buy things if you go into a shopping mall or a street full of shops (*Think* 1, 24). Learning language for learners pointed out the significance of language learning so that it is needed to be more aware of the role of language learning in educational contexts or other sectors (Chang et al., 2020). It means that both learning language and language learning are inseparable and have a close relationship. Therefore, the textbooks developed need to be considered with the values embedded in the learning materials because word choices and images used in the materials affect the interpretation which is internalized by the readers.

Textbooks have crucial aspects in education because they are used by teachers in managing the teaching and learning process in classrooms. Setyono & Widodo (2019) stated that teachers can manage teaching materials and utilize the textbooks in *in-class* and *out-class* activities as guiding for them. Even though the instructional materials are neither nor uniform since the change over the years; the word choices used account of feminist language reform and the materials developed could be based on the domain or different settings (Selvi & Kocaman, 2021). Textbooks that have bias orientation may lead to biased worldwide and individuals' perspectives (Baleghizadeh & Amiri Shayesteh, 2020). In terms of the issue, language textbooks are well-designed and well-developed to support engagement with culture and global science and values before those are distributed to the learners (Davidson & Liu, 2020) involving gender equality values.

The textbooks need to deliver a fair reflection of the world even though a few researchers or policymakers put their attention or paid to gender inequality in instructional materials used by schools and universities or other educational institutions in which the places are a core in shaping, reshaping, polishing the learners' ideas, beliefs, perspectives, attitudes, and behaviours (Orfan, 2021). Pictures and word choices put in the text form discourse that creates understanding and interpretation to the readers involving gender inequality contexts. Adriany (2019) supported that discourse has a close correlation to power that could marginalize anyone or anything different, for instance women are discredited because of their gender. Equal opportunity or fair treatment both for males and females is crucial to making a better life and a better world. Afterward, one of the best ways to support equality is through education by incorporating gender equality contexts in the textbooks.

Plenty of scholars conducted research on textbook analysis that represent gender inequality values (Sarvarzade & Wotipka, 2017); (Rahim & Daghigh, 2020); (Barton & Sakwa, 2012); (Baleghizadeh & Amiri Shayesteh, 2020); (Nguyen et al., 2021). Whereas, textbooks have a pivotal role in shaping students' perceptions and attitudes because they read the texts, observe the images, and could probably imitate what they read and observe. Every text and sentence or even illustrations developed are instilled in some values including gender inequality values because symbols and signs refer to the meanings. All components in the textbooks such as texts, images, colours, and sentences called semiotics mode (He & van Leeuwen, 2020) can influence the readers' or learners' ideology, beliefs, or attitudes. Textbooks are a stimulus and the reactions are the response of the pupils toward what they learn from the textbooks. Therefore, language choices and dictions used should be opted well to influence a good response to what they read.

Xiong & Peng (2020) note that the textbook developers requires engaging the readers in critically reflecting and negotiating cultural knowledge and meanings in which the meaning tends to empower the readers rather than disempower them. However, texts also could probably disempower the readers because the writers used the imbalance cultural representation contents in the textbooks developed. The imbalanced cultural representation have negative impact in educational sectors and gender

inequalities values including the perpetuation of stereotypes (Davidson & Liu, 2020). For paradigmatically and syntagmatically, the texts are built to the link a power-knowledge regime between writers and readers and built the values in the texts (Chen & Cheung, 2020).

Language and culture cannot be separated from one another because two of them are intertwined. Consequently, the culture is brought to the classroom in the teaching and learning process. The recognition that culture has a pivotal role and crucial aspects in language learning has been debated over the past few decades in the education field (Baleghizadeh & Amiri Shayesteh, 2020). Language can be either motivation or demotivation to the readers. Since language and culture so closely intertwined with a sense of self so that it could affect on confidence and motivation (Abdelhadi et al., 2019). Through those images, it could be self-motivation for men to be more powerful and instil the values to be implemented in their daily life. Certainly, learners particularly children bring in their perspectives and values when reading texts, and sentences and viewing pictures in the textbooks (Sarvarzade & Wotipka, 2017). Even though, they believe that the condition is less for teachers who applied conventional teaching methods that implement teacher-centred teaching methods and also for more malleable younger pupils.

Indonesia and other countries have the same struggle with gender inequality and inequity issues. It has been a long issue throughout the world. Therefore, gender-biased appear in school materials (Barton & Sakwa, 2012); (Lee, 2018); and (Lee & Collins, 2010) including in the textbooks. The textbooks for senior high schools were published by the Educational Ministry and written by a group of women. English textbooks for grade 10 were written by Utami Widiati, Zuliati Rohmah, and Furaidah; for grade 11 written by Mahrukh Bashir; and for grade 12 by Utami Widiati, Zuliati Rohmah, and Furaidah.

2. Method

2.1 Procedures

Senior High School textbooks were chosen to identify as the corpus of this study. The textbooks were published by the Government and disseminated to schools as the main materials to be learned by the students. Those were designed by Educational experts in developing and designing English materials approved by the Ministry of Education in Indonesia. The schoolbooks are the major resources for the learners and teachers in learning English in senior high schools. The materials available focus on four skills namely speaking, reading, listening, and writing that has 17 chapters. The three of primer materials contain the values of supporting the world to reach the targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). All the writers are women as proof that the government gave a chance to women to explore their abilities and skills.

There were 17 chapters in senior high school textbooks (Grade X, XI, and XI) selected as samples. The samples selected randomly based on odd and even numbers to generalize the research results. The content was classified into five categories namely visibility, firstness, social role, domestic roles, and masculine generic forms; afterward the data were carried out the systematic recording and tabulation of female and male characters and written in each selected chapter (Orfan, 2021). The data collection procedure was adopted by Orfan (2021). The textbooks analysis has five categories: (1) the number of appearances of both female and male characters in texts and pictures, (2) female and male social roles such as pilots, engineers, doctors, chef, babysitter, (3) female and male's domestics roles namely mother, father, sister, brother, uncle, (4) firstness such as her/him, father/mother, (5) masculine generic constructions such as (mankind, he) when referring to both females and males.

Johansson and Malmsjo (2009); Jones, Kitetu, and Sunderland (1995); Gupta and Yin (1990); Porecca (1984); Poulou (1997) conducted research related to ESL textbooks with a quantitative method in

which they counted the numbers of female and male characters in the textbooks but It is argued by Porecca (1984,713) mentioning that the survey study tends to fail in elaborating how females and males are presented (Barton & Sakwa, 2012). Consequently, this study used mixed research (quantitative and qualitative methods) to investigate the data in more detail so that using CDA was needed to compile this study. This research identifies to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the frequency or number of men-to-women appearances in the textbooks?
- (2) What are the common activities linked between men and women?
- (3) To what extent are males and females represented portrayed in the textbooks?

2.2 Data analysis

The content analysis was used to analyse the textbooks in this research. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) was also applied to this research to complement the content analysis (Barton & Sakwa, 2012). The data gained were cross-checked to ensure the accuracy and the manual analysis was conducted for all the males and females characters and corpus that appear in the written texts (Lee, 2018). The critical discourse analysis elaborates not only on the texts but also on the context of social condition in the place by considering the domain. A primarily qualitative, CDA-informed macro level approach, investigating how power relations and inequalities are discursively perpetuated and maintained in the society (Prendergast & Quinn, 2020).

3. Results

3.1 Visibility and Illustrations

The frequency of illustrations both one-character illustration and multi-character illustrations in the textbooks were counted by identifying and categorizing the pictures based on the category. The female and male pictures are divided into two categories namely one-character illustration and multi-character illustration. The illustrations were calculated for one-character for two sexes and then counted for multi-character pictures as well. The frequency for gender illustrations can be shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Females and Males Illustrations

Category	Gender	Grade X		Grade XI		Grade XII		In Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	Total	%
One-character illustration	Female	3	20	3	75	34	74	40	62
	Male	12	80	1	25	12	26	25	38
Total		15	100	4	100	46	100	65	100
Multi-character illustrations	Female	19	40	9	53	40	37	68	40
	Male	28	60	8	47	67	63	103	60
Total		47	100	17	100	107	100	171	100
N.Female character illustration: 108=46%					N.Male character illustration: 128=54%				

Both females and males have different calculation in terms of the number of men and women in the textbooks in which males' picture of one-character have significant differences to females (62% for females and 38% for males). However, in the multi-character illustrations, males' pictures dominated (60%) and female proportion (40%). Moreover, in the total number of females and males illustration reveal that men have higher percentage portrayed in the textbooks than women, 128 and 108 respectively.

In terms of the number of males and females names, male’s names are much more dominant mentioned in the textbook with the total 132 for females and 217 for males. The frequency of male and female’ names can be shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Female and Male’s Names

Textbooks	Female	Male
Grade X	37	173
Grade XI	11	5
Grade XII	84	39
Total	132=21%	217=79%

3.2 Social Role

In terms of the social role, female-monopolised ratio is more than male-monopolised with the average total 10 for females and 7 for males. However, related to male-dominated, men ratios are far more than women, 17 and 4 data respectively. For more detail of the social role is described in Table 3.

Table 3. Frequency of Social Role

Types of social roles	Grade X	Grade XI	Grade XII	Total
Female-monopolised	10			10
Male-monopolised	7			7
Female-dominated		1	1	2
Male-dominated	13	2	2	17

3.3 Domestic Roles

The textbooks have numerous domestic roles representation for both females and males. The findings of data can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Domestic Roles

Domestic roles of Females	Grade X	Grade XI	Grade XII	Domestic role of Males	Grade X	Grade XI	Grade XII
Mother	3		4	Father	7	1	4
Daughter	10		3	Son	3	1	9
Sister	28	1	2	Brother	2		
Niece				Nephew			
Housewife	4	4		Husband	1	1	
Grandmother	6		1	Grandfather	3	1	1
Granddaughter				Grandson			
Aunty				Uncle		1	
Total	51	5	10		16	5	14
N.Females of Domestic Roles: 66 =65%				N.Males of Domestic Roles: 35=35%			

The Table 4 illustrates the domestic roles of females and males in the textbooks for grade X, XI, and XII. The frequency of females in the domestic roles is double much more than the counterpart (males), 66 and 35 respectively.

3.4 Gender Firstness

In the textbooks, there are some pronouns identified such as she, he, her, him, hers, his, himself, and herself. The frequency of the pronouns (firstness) is portrayed in Table 5 and 6.

Table 5. Frequency Gender Firstness for Females

Textbooks	She	Her	Hers	Herself	Total
Grade X	41	64	1		106
Grade XI	5	5			10
Grade XII	32	33		2	67
Total	78=43%	102=56%	1=0%	2=1%	182=100%

The Table 5 shows the frequency gender firstness for women, it shows that there are plenty of female pronouns in the textbooks such as *she*, *her*, *hers*, and *herself*. The object pronoun (her) was written more than the subject pronoun with total number 102 and 78. While, there were few of pronoun “hers and herself” portrayed in the textbooks. As a result, the total of female gender firstness in the textbooks is 182. Meanwhile, the frequency of males’ gender firstness can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Frequency Gender Firstness for Males

Textbooks	He	Him	His	Himself	Total
Grade X	82	48	44		174
Grade XI	5	1	1		7
Grade XII	33	11	11	1	56
Total	120=51%	60=25%	56=24%	1=0%	237=100%

In terms of males’ gender firstness, the Table 6 illustrates the calculation of male pronouns in the textbooks. There are 120 of subject pronoun “he” mentioned in the textbooks and 60 for object pronoun “him”. Meanwhile, possessive pronouns “his” are written 56 and “himself” only 1 as the datum. Therefore, the total number of the male pronouns tendency is 237. Compared to female gender firstness for women in the Table 5, frequency of males’ firstness are more than women with 237 for males and 182 for females.

3.5 Masculine Generic Construction

Another category related to masculine generic construction is also provided in the textbooks that the result is described in Table 7.

Table 7. Masculine Generic Construction

Masculine Generic Constructions	Grade X	Grade XI	Grade XII	Total
Cavemen	1			1
Policemen	3			3
Mankind	4			4

Table 7 shows that there is no masculine generic construction for grade X and XII. However, there are three masculine generic constructions in the textbook grade X namely cavemen (1), policemen (3), and mankind (4).

4. Discussion

The values embedded in the textbooks have a big role that designs the textbooks because those affect on the texts, the pictures, and the word choices used. Even though all of the textbook developers are women, the images and content tend to gender inequality and inequity contexts. There is a remarkable gap in the textbooks based on the quantitative data identified in which some aspects of the textbooks illustrated gender inequality practices. The textbooks designed to become more unequal between men and women proportion. The frequency and the total number of females are fewer than males in most of the items. The total number of females and males illustration reveal that men have a higher percentage portrayed in the textbooks than women, 108 and 128 respectively and it is the same as the names used in which males' names (217) and females (132). It is supported also by the data of gender firstness frequency where women have 182 data and 237 for their counterpart.

The names of males also are much more than females based in Table 2 and it is supported by the frequency of gender firstness for males (237) and females (182) in Table 5. Even though all the writers of the textbooks are females but some aspects such as pictures, names, and gender firstness are still dominated by men. Many misconceptions of gender roles and occupational pursuits are cultivated through symbol vicarious modelling of stereotypes demonstrated by character models that could be interpreted, followed and implemented by children in their daily lives (Lee, 2020). We realize that our perspectives are different from numerous school curricula where not all texts or other aspects in the textbooks are values equal (Bezemer & Cowan, 2020).

Even though, when females are more mentioned as central characters (Table 3) and (Table 4) but they are often described in stereotypical ways in the textbooks. For instance, women tend to be portrayed in domestic roles such as cleaning the houses (chapter 5, grade 12), shopping (chapter 7, grade 12), getting married (chapter 2, grade 10), and taking care of children (chapter 2, grade 11). Lee (2020, p.2) reinforces that “females were also associated with domestic roles”. It is relevant to the research results of (Lee, 2018) conducting scrutiny investigation in the three textbooks analysed. The number of female domestic roles are double than the counterpart which is 65% and 35%. Therefore, in the materials provided many of inequality dealing with the women stereotypes.

The research results reveal that there is hidden gender stereotyping contained in the textbooks in which men were depicted as more powerful than women such as the father put up the tent or went fishing with his sons while the mother's tasks seem to be domestic roles cooking and childrearing. These findings also are similar to (Lee, 2020) that women are still frequently placed in family roles than men in which there are much more aunts, and grandmothers than their counterparts. The domestic roles lead to where a member of the family work and stays at home to accomplish home duties without any charge. In a patriarchy society, this role tends to do by women. As a result, based on the data, the content of the textbooks are still adopted traditional stereotypes.

The four types of social roles are female-monopolised, male-monopolised, female-dominated, and male-dominated. The data portray that between females and males has a small difference with 10 and 7 data; however, in terms of the dominated in social role, men dominated in social roles eight times than women. The materials in schoolbooks still represented of stereotypes because the trend of male domination seems to be showed by the writers. Consequently, this will affect on the students' beliefs and attitude in the future. If men and women are unequally represented in textbooks, pupils including girls grow up with mentality that men as a dominant group are better and more powerful and capable than those of other groups (Orfan, 2021).

Images, portraits, or landscapes are a pivotal media in shaping people's perspectives and beliefs because every picture has various interpretations and values. As a result, these are crucial to select relevant images in the books because pupils instil the values to what they read and interpret all components in the materials including symbols, signs, and images. In these three textbooks, plenty of images illustrate males' domination. The visual images receive less attention from research investigating gender imbalance in textbooks (Li, 2016). Almost all of the pictures selected at the beginning of the chapter are men revealing men's power and domination in everyday life. For instance, on pages 29, 38, 50, 81, 108, and any other chapters, almost all the pictures are men. The illustrations of the pictures can be seen in Picture 1.

Picture 1: Male domination pictures

In the textbooks, the data show that men are breadwinners and women stay at home as housewives or households that identically with shopping, cooking, and taking care of the children. The pictures represent men are more powerful than women because only men are represented as travellers, announcers, fishers, hunters, soldiers, idols, and others. It is relevant to the patriarchy condition in Indonesia that women as subordinate in society in which women have boundaries to do something because of their gender. Mai & Brundrett (2020, p.3) state that “gender stereotype and patriarchal attitudes have a strong influence on the society, there is still way to go”. Those influence people's perspectives and the perspectives might influence the materials designed. Consequently, it is believed that textbooks have a pivotal role in formal education (Lee, 2014) to drive and control the students' perspectives and behaviours.

In terms of the data reveal that there were no women described in military-related jobs or hunter-hobbies such as fishing or climbing mountains. Soldiers with gun are portrayed with men's illustrations or climbing mountains with men's representation in the books which mean it is believed that only men can do the tasks or activities. It means that males are more dominant in the course books because pictures are dominated by men with big muscular and powerful who are supposed as breadwinners and described in occupations. Kostas (2019) presents the research results of the narratives to reinforce the spatial binary of public normalization that females as homemakers and domesticity or male as breadwinners, protectors, and providers. In terms of occupations, women tend to work in jobs involving nurturing, service, and support but men are illustrated involved in physically-demanding jobs such as farmer, soldier, hunter, climber, and other physical jobs that indicate to be more powerful (Lee & Collins, 2010). This condition also is relevant to (Li, 2016) that

there were no images of women depicted in military-related jobs in both textbooks in the 1980s and 2000s.

Almost in every chapter, male pictures in the textbooks cover are described as men’s activities such as a pantomime (p.182), an idol or an artist (p.108), travellers/climbers (p.50), and many others. Then, women were described as very feminine because they tend to go shopping, get married, wear pink, and others characteristics. Nayak & Surendran (2021) mention this linguistics condition as linguistic-based bias in which the writers use masculine words and generic pronouns to exclude the role and the importance of women. In the patriarchal society, women are formed with the ideal behaviour and habit such as women tend to stay at home, become fashionable, serve for her husband, and other stereotyped as women’s jobs (Andersson, 2020); in the early 1970s, women are portrayed as an object to sell or buying clothes, to manage the house, to serve family and as sexual partner (Greubel, 2021). It is similar also to a poem of “A Freedom Song” which illustrates an exploitative domestic situation of women (Barton & Sakwa, 2012). With the same condition as the findings of the research (see e.g Lee, 2018 and Gailea & Rasyid, 2015). It means that gender imbalance still exists in the schoolbooks although the writers of the textbooks are women and the government supports the SDGs’ targets of gender balance.

In expressing feelings and ideas, it is not only to be expressed through words or sentences but also it could be devoted to symbols, colours, and pictures. Words, phrases, gestures, pictures, and symbols refer to the referential meaning, as Riley (2019, p.3) notes that “The most important feature that distinguishes humans from all other forms of life on the planet is our capacity for evolving referential language”. The meaning of the words, objects, or images refers to the referential meaning which means every object has the meaning that is based on the referee. Swenson & Cipolla (2020) state symbols are more closely to Saussure’s semiology where every sign or symbol expresses a meaning which corresponds to convention, tradition and culture of the place.

5. Conclusion

Textbooks have a big impact on students’ perspectives and behaviors because they gain some information and obtain the values from the texts and images available. Afterward, the values can be guidance for the students and they might be implemented by the learners in their daily life. Consequently, the content of the schoolbooks is necessary to be considered by all stakeholders, especially for the developers to select the contents and contexts of the textbooks. Based on the research result, the proportion of men’s names and pictures in the textbooks for grade X, XI, XII of senior high schools are much more than female names and pictures. Men are more dominant in the social roles portrayed in the texts. The gender stereotype identified in the analysis of the textbooks is that women are put in the domestic roles such as cleaning the house, serving their husbands, taking care of the children, and other domestic roles. Meanwhile, men are illustrated as powerful people who are identical to going for the hunter, becoming an idol, fishing, and becoming breadwinners.

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